

Thermal network for natural convection during engine soak-back

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ABSTRACT

The paper deals with research activities for developing numerical models able to reproduce soak back phenomena after engine switch off and particularly taking natural convection into account in the engine core through 0D/1D network.

An approach is built from the analytical modelling of natural convection proposed by Yovanovich [1] for free field and numerical study of a simple configuration to take into account the confinement effect. The application of this modelling is presented on the whole core flow of an aeronautics gas turbine.

The work is realized in the framework of Tech TP development as short range Regional Turboprop Demonstrator of Engines Integrated Technology Demonstrator (ITD) within the Clean Sky 2 program.

Figure 1. Tech TP ©, the turboprop demonstrator currently being developed by Safran Helicopters as part of the Clean Sky 2 research programme

1. INTRODUCTION

A wide number of sources give correlations to model heat transfer under natural convection for classical shapes. Nevertheless, for complex 3D shapes, it is often difficult and random to assess natural convection with reasonable accuracy. In addition, provided correlations

generally stand for natural convection in free-field with an infinite ambient temperature and pressure.

In the current paper, the problem focuses on the natural convection inside a complex 3D object. Therefore, the natural convection creates fluid heating and flow circulation but restrictions induce pressure losses. To correctly predict the cooling time of the structure, the coupled problem should be considered since buoyancy forces directly drive the mass flow rate through the flow path.

First of all, the geometry based approach of Yovanovich [1] is detailed as reference for free-field natural convection. Then confinement behaviour laws including adverse gradient pressure are established thanks to a parametric CFD study on a simple case (vertical duct). Finally, the application on the engine soak-back is presented.

2. NATURAL CONVECTION THEORY

2.1. Definitions

Considering any object of wetted surface A , the thermo-fluidic problem is determined by 3 dimensionless numbers: Reynolds, Nusselt and Rayleigh ones.

$$Re_{\sqrt{A}} = \frac{V\sqrt{A}}{\nu} \quad Nu_{\sqrt{A}} = \frac{h\sqrt{A}}{\lambda}$$

$$Ra_{\sqrt{A}} = \frac{g\beta|T_w - T_0|\sqrt{A}^3}{\nu\alpha}$$

2.2. Free-field Nusselt/Rayleigh correlation

Reference [1] gives the general formulation for any object linking Nusselt number to Rayleigh one:

$$Nu_{\sqrt{A}} = Nu_{\sqrt{A}}^{\infty} + F(Pr) G_{\sqrt{A}} Ra_{\sqrt{A}}^{1/4} \quad (1)$$

Where $Nu_{\sqrt{A}}^{\infty}$ is the conductive limit, F is a Prandtl function:

$$F(Pr) = \frac{0.67}{[1+(0.5/Pr)^{9/16}]^{4/9}} \quad (2)$$

and G is the Body Gravity Function (BGF), dependant on object geometry:

$$G_{\sqrt{A}} = \left[\frac{1}{A} \iint_A \left(\frac{P(\theta)}{\sqrt{A}} \sin \theta \right)^{1/3} dA \right]^{3/4} \quad (3)$$

A is the wet surface, θ the angle between surface normal and gravity direction and $P(\theta)$ the length on the surface with such a normal.

To simplify notation, we can define Nusselt convective only number:

$$Nu_{\sqrt{A}}^{conv} = Nu_{\sqrt{A}} - Nu_{\sqrt{A}}^{\infty}$$

2.3. Body-gravity function definition

To calculate the BGF, [2] contains combination laws for serial or parallel flows, considering the boundary layer course.

For parallel flow arrangement, the formula is:

$$G_{\sqrt{A}} = \sum_{i=1}^N G_{\sqrt{A_i}} \left(\frac{A_i}{A} \right)^{7/8} \quad (4)$$

For series flow arrangement, the formula is:

$$G_{\sqrt{A}} = \left[\sum_{i=1}^N G_{\sqrt{A_i}}^{4/3} \left(\frac{A_i}{A} \right)^{7/6} \right]^{3/4} \quad (5)$$

Nevertheless, the definition of $P(\theta)$ is quite imperfect for complex shapes which are not defined by evident equation. A strategy will be proposed in §4.3 to generalize its formulation.

2.4. Confinement impact

An extension of Eq. 1 is proposed for natural convection inside annuli [4] or Cartesian enclosures [9]. Two asymptotic convective Nusselt regimes are described: duct regime (named transition in [4]) and boundary layer (BL) regime. With Yovanovich notation, it gives:

$$Nu_{\sqrt{A}}^{conv} = [Nu_{duct}^{-n} + Nu_{bl}^{-n}]^{-1/n} \quad (6)$$

Where Nu_{bl} is the Rayleigh dependant term of Eq. 1:

$$Nu_{bl} = F(Pr) G_{\sqrt{A}} Ra_{\sqrt{A}}^{1/4}$$

Nu_{duct} is a linear term of Rayleigh, and n is the combination parameter of the composite solution technique of Churchill and Usagi [7] ($n=2$ in [4], $n=1$ in [9]).

Thus we will search a correlation of the type:

$$Nu_{\sqrt{A}}^{conv} =$$

$$\left[(k_{Nu} Ra_{\sqrt{A}})^{-n} + \left(F(Pr) G_{\sqrt{A}} Ra_{\sqrt{A}}^{1/4} \right)^{-n} \right]^{-1/n} \quad (7)$$

3. FULL FORMULATION DETERMINATION

3.1. “Chimney” test case

To obtain simple behaviours due to confinement and adverse pressure gradient in a natural convection driven flow, CFD computations are performed on a 2D vertical duct with heated wall. Several aspect ratios d/L between 0.01 and 0.5 are studied, and Rayleigh variation given in Tab. 1 is obtained modifying the global scale of the model (with unchanged boundary conditions).

Channel length L (m)	Rayleigh number Ra_L
0.01	3.05×10^2
0.025	4.77×10^3
0.05	3.81×10^4
0.1	3.05×10^5
0.25	4.77×10^6
0.5	3.81×10^7
1	3.05×10^8

Table 1. Simulated Rayleigh number in function of channel length L

Meshes are structured ones and contain between 8.000 and 30.000 rectangular cells. Cell wall distance is 0.1% of height for all meshes and the vertical discretization is uniform with 200 cells.

Ansys Fluent solver is used for the calculations. Ideal gas law is applied with constant fluid properties. k- ω SST models turbulence when necessary.

In free-field 2D case with a linear object of length L , Eqs. 1 & 3 become:

$$Nu = Nu_L = Nu_L^{\infty} + F(Pr) G_L Ra_L^{1/4}$$

$$G_L = \left[\frac{\sin \theta}{L} \right]^{1/4}$$

Reynolds number will be defined using the channel hydraulic diameter D which directly links Reynolds number and linear flow rate q :

$$Re = Re_D = \frac{VD}{\nu} = \frac{4q}{\nu}$$

3.2. Nusselt & Reynolds correlation without adverse pressure gradient

We can see on Fig. 2 the two asymptotic regimes followed by the convective Nusselt number. For high Rayleigh number, the correlation proposed by [1] is well respected. For low Rayleigh number, the Nusselt number not only respects a linear correlation but also superimposes when plotted as function of Rayleigh number based on the width of the channel with a coefficient of 0.078.

Figure 2. Convective Nusselt number as function of Ra_D (left) and Ra_L (right) for 3 aspect ratios (0.01, 0.1 & 0.5) and asymptotic lines

In addition, we can note on Fig. 3 that Reynolds number behaves exactly similarly than Nusselt number:

$$Re = \left[\left(k_{Re}^{duct} Ra_D \right)^{-n} + \left(k_{Re}^{bl} Ra_L^{1/4} \right)^{-n} \right]^{-1/n} \quad (7)$$

with coefficients $k_{Re}^{duct} \approx 0.043$ and $k_{Re}^{bl} \approx 10$.

Figure 3. Reynolds number as function of Ra_D (left) and Ra_L (right) for 3 aspect ratios (0.01, 0.1 & 0.5) and asymptotic lines

To best fit the maximum of configurations, the combination parameter is chosen to $n=0.75$.

The impact of combination parameter on Fig. 4 on the case $d/L=0.5$ for $n=0.3, 0.75$ and 2.0 .

Figure 4. Combination parameter impact on Reynolds correlation for $d/L=0.5$ – $n=0.3, 0.75$ and 2.0

The result of the correlation with $n=0.75$ is given for Nusselt number on the Fig. 5.

Figure 5. Nusselt correlation for $d/L=0.5$ with $n=0.75$

The different regimes clearly appear on the temperature fields given in Fig. 6.

Figure 6. Dimensionless temperature field for $L/d=0.5$ in duct regime (left), intermediate (center) and BL one (right)

The critical aspect ratio associated with a Rayleigh number for which the flow passes from duct to BL regime is given by the equality of both Reynolds terms:

$$k_{Re}^{duct} Ra_D = k_{Re}^{bl} Ra_L^{1/4}$$

$$\Rightarrow k_{Re}^{duct} Ra_L \left(\frac{D}{L} \right)^3 = k_{Re}^{bl} Ra_L^{1/4}$$

Therefore:

$$\left(\frac{D}{L} \right)_{crit} = \sqrt[3]{ \frac{k_{Re}^{bl}}{k_{Re}^{duct}} } Ra_L^{-1/4} \quad (8)$$

3.3. Adverse pressure gradient impact

Buoyancy force implies that a maximum pressure gradient could be opposed to the ascendant flow (beyond which the flow is necessary descendant wherever):

$$\Delta P_{max} = gL\Delta\rho = gL\rho_0\beta\Delta T = \frac{\mu a}{L^2} Ra_L$$

Computations are launched for $0 < \Delta P / \Delta P_{max} < 0.9$. Fig. 7 shows that the following simple behaviour is respected for the Nusselt number:

$$\frac{Nu}{Nu_0} = 1 - \frac{\Delta P}{\Delta P_{max}} \quad (9)$$

Subscript 0 means without adverse gradient.

Figure 7. Nusselt deviation under adverse gradient pressure for various length ($d/L=0.1$)

For Reynolds number, the same correlation can be applied in the duct regime:

$$\frac{Re}{Re_0} = 1 - \frac{\Delta P}{\Delta P_{max}} \text{ if } \frac{D}{L} < \left(\frac{D}{L}\right)_{crit} \quad (10)$$

In the boundary layer regime, the global flow rate quickly drops down even for low adverse gradient since a descending flow occurs in the unheated zone.

Eq. 10 can be extended in intermediate regime defining a slope coefficient A linking both modes where L_{crit} is given by Eq. 8:

$$A = \min\left(1; \frac{2}{\pi} \tan^{-1}\left[-K \ln\left(\frac{L}{L_{crit}}\right)\right] + 1\right) \quad (11)$$

The Reynolds correlation becomes:

$$\frac{Re}{Re_0} = \max\left[A\left(1 - \frac{\Delta P}{\Delta P_{max}}\right); 1 - \frac{\Delta P}{\Delta P_{max}}\left(1 - \frac{1}{A} + \frac{1}{A^2}\right)\right] \quad (12)$$

Comparison of CFD results and proposed correlation is given on Fig. 8 for $d/L=0.1$ using the best fitting coefficient $K=0.6$ in Eq. 11:

Figure 8. Reynolds deviation under adverse gradient pressure and proposed correlation for various length ($d/L=0.1$) - $K=0.6$

Finally, Reynolds/ ΔP behaviour looks like pump characteristics curve $Q=f(\Delta P)$. Thenceforth, each vertical cavity with natural convection can be seen as a generator component of the pneumatic network for which the dimensionless power P^* defined in Eq. 13 is illustrated on Fig. 9:

Figure 9. Dimensionless power of natural convection and proposed correlation for various length ($d/L=0.1$)

P^* is defined as the ratio of the effective power by the maximum theoretical power:

$$P^* = \frac{Q\Delta P}{Q_0\Delta P_{max}} = \frac{Re}{Re_0} \frac{\Delta P}{\Delta P_{max}} \quad (13)$$

3.4. General formulations for 2D cases

For the duct regime, Fig. 6 shows that the temperature is quickly saturated at the wall temperature.

The outlet temperature being equal to the wall temperature, the heat flux balance gives:

$$4Nu = Re.Pr$$

Then, considering the whole fluid tends to wall temperature, the vertical force analysis gives (for laminar pressure losses):

$$Re = \frac{\sin \alpha}{32Pr} Ra_D$$

And thus:

$$Nu = \frac{\sin \alpha}{128} Ra_D$$

For $\alpha=90^\circ$ (vertical duct), coefficients are $k_{Re}^{duct}=0.043$ and $k_{Nu}=0.0078$.

For the BL regime, the enthalpy balance closure can be written:

$$\Phi = hLP\Delta T = c_p \iint_{outlet} \rho(T - T_0)\vec{V}\cdot\vec{n} dS$$

Hence:

$$\frac{4Nu}{Re.Pr} = \frac{\iint_{outlet} \rho(T - T_0)\vec{V}\cdot\vec{n} dS}{W\Delta T} = K_{bl}$$

Where K_{bl} depends on velocity and temperature profiles in the boundary layer. For the vertical channel, K_{bl} is measured at 60% and 80% of the height on the case $d/L=0.5$ from the profiles given on Fig. 10:

$$K_{bl} \approx 0.40 \pm 0.01$$

Figure 10. Vertical velocity (top) and dimensionless temperature (bottom) profiles for $L/d=0.5$ at 60% and 80% of the channel height ($Ra=3.10^8$)

Finally:

$$Nu^{conv} = \left[\left(\frac{\sin \alpha}{128} Ra_D \right)^{-n} + \left(F(Pr) G_L Ra_L^{1/4} \right)^{-n} \right]^{-1/n}$$

$$Re = \left[\left(\frac{\sin \alpha}{32Pr} Ra_D \right)^{-n} + \left(\frac{4F(Pr)}{K_{bl}Pr} G_L Ra_L^{1/4} \right)^{-n} \right]^{-1/n}$$

3.5. General formulations for 3D cases

For 3D problem using \sqrt{A} as reference length, the equations are:

$$Nu_{\sqrt{A}} = K_{bl} \frac{S_w}{A} Re_{\sqrt{A}} Pr$$

With S_w the cross-section of the channel and $K_{bl}=1$ for the duct regime.

Then, for the duct regime:

$$Re_{\sqrt{A}} = \frac{\sin \alpha}{32Pr} \frac{D}{\sqrt{A}} Ra_{\sqrt{A}} \quad (14)$$

$$Nu_{\sqrt{A}} = \frac{\sin \alpha}{32} \frac{DS_w}{A\sqrt{A}} Ra_{\sqrt{A}} \quad (15)$$

And for the BL regime:

$$Re_{\sqrt{A}} = \frac{A}{S_w} \frac{F(Pr)}{K_{bl}Pr} G_{\sqrt{A}} Ra_{\sqrt{A}}^{1/4} \quad (16)$$

3.6. Modelling strategy

For a given cavity inside a component, knowing upstream and wall temperatures, the Rayleigh number $Ra_{\sqrt{A}}$ can be computed. Then Eqs. 14-16 give Reynolds without pressure gradient from geometry-based coefficients.

Eqs. 12-13 provide necessary data to set up the pneumatic network of the studied product which will compute the pressure value at each node and the mass flow rate between nodes (i.e. advective conductances).

Finally, Eq. 1-9-15 will permit to define convective conductances associated with Rayleigh number and pressure gradient.

Therefore, it is possible to entirely define a thermo-pneumatic network solving natural convection in confined environment, based on geometric coefficient, even if some parameters should be calibrated or further studied (n, K_{bl}).

We can note that time aspects have not been addressed. The previous strategy must be reproduced for each time step according to an implicit or explicit scheme. Thermal inertias have to be considered in the resolution as well as dynamic inertia which should be defined (viscosity will probably delays behaviours).

4. APPLICATION TO SOAK-BACK

The modelling is applied on the engine RTM322 © on which experimental measures of soak-back phase exist.

Figure 11. RTM322 © schematic cut and main characteristics – Courtesy of Safran Helicopter Engines

The experimental bench is composed of the engine located on a rotorcraft representative compartment (Fig. 12), the whole placed in a close engine test bench as illustrated on Fig. 13. The soak-back phenomenon stands for the thermal transient phase starting by the engine switch-off. During soak-back, strong vertical gradient can appear and some parts can experience maximal thermal constraint given the lack of cooling.

Figure 12. RTM322 © test device – Courtesy of Safran Helicopter Engines

Figure 13. Test facility

4.1. Network assumptions

The engine core flow contains:

- The vein domain crossed by the blade rows and connected to the ambience by the intake and the exhaust.
- The secondary air system composed of rotor and stator cavities mainly axisymmetric.

Each cavity is modelled by 4 nodes separating the zone in 90° sectors in a X-shape: top and bottom ones essentially horizontal and right and left ones mostly vertical. We consider the fluid enters by the bottom sector and exhausts by the top one.

Figure 14. Schematic representation of a turbine module – real flow paths during soak-back (left) and nodal discretisation (right) where yellow diamonds are fluid nodes and red arrows are mass flow rates

Cavities are linked by restrictions characterized by their sections.

The full model should contain:

- 300 nodes (75 by sector),
- At least as much of convections (300),
- 850 axial advectons (in one sector considering both directions – unknown *a priori*),
- 300 angular advectons (between sectors).

4.2. Conductive limit

The Nusselt conductive limit is obtained using h_{eq} in its definition where:

$$h_{eq} = \frac{\lambda}{l_{eq}}$$

l_{eq} being the equivalent conductive length.

- Annular cavities

For annular cavities, we assumed that $l_{eq}=K_l D$ with $0 < K_l < 1$ and thus:

$$Nu_{\sqrt{A}}^{\infty} = \frac{h\sqrt{A}}{\lambda} = \frac{\sqrt{A}}{K_l D} = \frac{P_w \sqrt{A}}{4S_w K_l}$$

Assuming the cross section S_w and the wetted perimeter P_w have the same gravity radii, the Guldin theorem [10] gives:

$$\frac{S_w}{P_w} = \frac{V}{A}$$

Hence:

$$Nu_{\sqrt{A}}^{\infty} = \frac{h\sqrt{A}}{\lambda} = \frac{\sqrt{A}}{K_l D} = \frac{A\sqrt{A}}{4K_l V} \quad (17)$$

- bladed cavities

The conduction can be seen as the parallel conductance of axisymmetric walls and blades walls which gives:

$$Nu_{\sqrt{A}}^{\infty} = Nu_{axi}^{\infty} + Nu_{blades}^{\infty}$$

The 1st term is given by Eq. 17. The 2nd terms should be computed on each blade row. 3D Finite Element Models (FEM) have been built for the fluid surrounding 1 compressor stator blade (Fig. 15) and 1 rotor blade and compared with 2D FEM of the median cut. Table 2 shows the results of conductive Nusselt. 2D approach could be sufficient given other approximations.

Figure 15. 3D Finite Element Model of 1 stator blade

Nu_{blades}^{∞}	FEM 3D	FEM 2D	deviation
Stator blade	10.97	11.33	3.6%
Rotor blade	2.72	2.88	5.9%

Table 2. Conductive Nusselt estimation for blades – 2D/3D comparison

4.3. Body-gravity function

- annular cavities

Assuming rectangular base annuli composed with 4 walls (upstream, downstream, inner and outer) the BGF can be computed by sector and then by wall using the combination laws (Eqs. 4-5). For top and bottom zones, 2 parallel flows are assumed and wall boundary layers are in serial. For vertical zones, boundary layers are considered in parallel.

For any annulus base shape, the BGF is approximated with the closer rectangular base annulus.

- bladed cavities

For bladed cavities, same combination laws can be applied but need the BGF of the blades alone. Nevertheless Eq. 3 requires a mathematical definition of the surface to determine $P(\theta)$. The following section

will present an approach to evaluate the BGF on any object from its surface mesh.

First of all, the θ definition locally translates by:

$$\theta = \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{|\vec{g} \cdot \vec{n}|}{\|\vec{g}\|} \right)$$

Then the perimeter $P(\theta)$ is defined by surface integral:

$$P(\theta_i) = \lim_{\delta\theta \rightarrow 0} \iint_{\theta_i - \frac{\delta\theta}{2}}^{\theta_i + \frac{\delta\theta}{2}} \frac{\|\vec{v}_\theta\|}{\delta\theta} dA$$

And integral of BGF is replace by a sum on the angular increments $\delta\theta$:

$$G_{\sqrt{A}} = \left[\frac{1}{A} \iint_A [P(\theta) \sin \theta]^{1/3} dA \right]^{3/4} \approx \left(\sum_{\theta_i} \widetilde{A}_{\theta_i} [P(\theta_i)]^{1/3} \right)^{3/4}$$

With

$$\widetilde{A}_{\theta_i} = \iint_{\theta_i - \frac{\delta\theta}{2}}^{\theta_i + \frac{\delta\theta}{2}} (\sin \theta)^{1/3} dA$$

This formulation is firstly validated on a sphere for which the perimeter $P(\theta)$ has a mathematical solution: $P(\theta) = 4\pi R \sin(\theta)$.

Figure 16. Sphere discretisation by slices for $\delta\theta=3^\circ$

The perimeter is then computed for several values of the angular increment: 1, 2, 3 and 5° .

Figure 17. $P(\theta)$ computation on a sphere mesh generated with 1° resolution for several angular increments and theoretical value

We can see on Fig. 17 that the formulation works well except near the degeneracy points 0 and 90° .

Then the approach is applied on a compressor blade (Fig. 18) to compute the BGF as a function of its azimuthal position α .

Figure 18. Compressor blade surface mesh for 3° resolution – Around 2 million of triangles

The results for 3 angular increments are compared on Fig. 19 with a radial cylinder and a plane plate with the same height and mean incidence (30°) as the blade.

We can note that BGF computation gives noisy results for $\alpha=-90$ and $\alpha=90^\circ$. Elsewhere BGF behaviour is quite similar to a radial cylinder or the inclined plate.

Figure 19. Compressor blade BGF for $\delta\theta=1, 3$ and 5° compared with cylinder and inclined plate BGF as a function of azimuthal position

The BGF $G_{\sqrt{A}}(\alpha)$ can also be plotted in radar representation given in Fig. 20. Considering the BGF is a continuous function the combination laws Eqs. 4-5 can be re-written with integrals for each 90° sector Σ where N is the number of blades of the row.

For top and bottom sectors (parallel flow arrangement), the formula is:

$$G_{\sqrt{A_{\Sigma}}} = 4^{7/8} N^{1/8} \frac{2}{\pi} \int_{\alpha \in \Sigma} G_{\sqrt{A_i}}(\alpha) d\alpha$$

For side sectors (serial flow arrangement), we obtain:

$$G_{\sqrt{A_{\Sigma}}} = 4^{7/8} N^{-1/8} \left[\frac{2}{\pi} \int_{\alpha \in \Sigma} G_{\sqrt{A_i}}^3(\alpha) d\alpha \right]^{3/4}$$

Figure 20. Radar plot of BGF for a compressor blade in function of azimuthal position

4.4. Planned validation/Calibration process

In parallel of the nodal network definition, high fidelity aerothermal simulations of the soak-back phase are performed using Lattice-Boltzmann Method (LBM) with PowerFlow/PowerTherm solver developed by Dassault Systemes. First resolution level addresses only the flow outside the engine (compartment + test facility) as illustrated on Fig. 21.

Figure 21. Velocity field (top) and temperature field (bottom) in the engine compartment and test facility at 15.5s after engine shut-down – PowerFlow solver [11]

This approach has been completed and is fully documented in [11].

Currently, the 2nd resolution level is being developed with the addition of engine inner flow and the whole structure (thermal coupling). Once the computation will be done, detailed data will be available.

Then the 3rd resolution step consists in replacing the inner flow detailed modelling by the nodal network. Comparison of results with the ones of the 2nd step will allow the validation of the low fidelity approach. Influence studies will highlight some undefined coefficient of the methodology (K_{bl} in Eq. 16, K_l in Eq. 17). Some correction coefficients could also be introduced in function of deviation analysis.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on previous works presented in the 1st part, the chapter 3 presents a theoretical approach to solve the thermo-pneumatics coupled problem of natural convection in confined domain.

The last part tries to cover some aspects of its actual application on the complex 3D geometry constituted by the core flow of a turboshaft engine during the soak-back phase.

The current project aims at achieving its validation and calibration thanks to LBM reference computations before applying it on a turboprop configuration to support Tech TP development.

All or part of this approach could be used on a large range of industrial configurations to enhance thermal modelling accuracy.

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